

THE PREVALENCE OF BETA-THALASSEMIA BURDEN IN INDIA: A META-ANALYSIS WITH 17, 11, 536 SUBJECTS.

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ABSTRACT

Aims: *Thalassemia is an inherited hemoglobin disorder caused by anomalies in the globin chain and affects 4.5% of the population across the map. Each year, India reports more than 9000–10000 thalassemia major births. The frequency and prevalence of thalassemia in India have not been well examined previously. The study outcome could have aid in designing healthcare policies to cope with the thalassemia burden.*

Method *Of 17,11,536 subjects were included after depicted 45 most relevant studies in this meta-analysis. Among the included studies, 16 was carried out in different educational institutions. For statistical derivation meta and metaphor was used.*

Result *The forest plot showed a high heterogeneity in Indian prevalence rate of beta-thalassemia. Funnel diagrams were used to estimate the publication bias for the included studies.*

The overall heterogeneity in the prevalence rate of beta-thalassemia occurrence in this meta-analysis was 0.4238 (95% CI = 0.1334–0.2462; I² = 99.99%; p-value < 0.001). Using regression analysis Z score 4.5972 was derived, with significant asymmetry (p < 0.001) to plot the funnel plot.

Discussion *This meta-analysis describes the real scenario of thalassemia prevalence as the three subgroups of the study shows significant different in the prevalence of the disorder.*

The prevalence was successfully reduced through education and testing for this disease and most importantly, an extensive registration program and rigorous monitoring are necessary to combat thalassemia.

Conclusion

The beta-thalassemia leads to serious health and financial burden and worsens in the coming decade. Efforts are needed to develop awareness-raising and screening initiatives. This study will be very relevant in revealing the burden of beta-thalassemia in India.

Keywords: Meta-analysis, beta-thalassemia, Mutation, Publication bias

1. INTRODUCTION

Thalassemia is an inherited hemoglobin disorder caused by anomalies in the globin chain and affects 4.5% of the population across the map (1,2). In India nearly 9000 - 10000 major

thalassemia births each year, cause a huge burden by demanding many transferable blood stock as well as associate medication. In the general Indian population, the carrier frequencies for thalassemia vary from 0 to 5% make parity with global frequency but Some communities have higher carrier frequencies. Like Mahar, Koli, and Agri are from Maharashtra, Gowda and Lingayat are from Karnataka (3,4) have the carrier frequencies of 9.3% and 9% respectively (3). According to Ghotbi and Tsukatani (5), the Arora sub-caste in Punjab has the highest prevalence of the thalassemia trait, reaching close to 47.8% of the population.

The lack of knowledge about the condition, its symptoms, survival rate, treatment options, and psychosocial and cultural issues among the public, including high- and low-risk communities and healthcare professionals, lack of follow-up may make it more difficult to perform proper strategies against the disorder (6,7, 8, 9). Several countries have mandatory screening programs followed by counseling. Italy, Greece, Canada, Great Britain, and Cyprus have all benefited from these initiatives. Cyprus lowered the prevalence of the disease from high to non-existent after implementing a screening program (10,11,12,13,14).

More than 350 mutations are depicted as responsible for thalassemia, but in India — IVS 1–5 G C, IVS 1–1-G T, Codon 41/42 (- TCTT), Codon 8/9, and the 619 bp deletion—constitute more than 90% mutations in thalassemia. (5–12) The most prevalent beta-thalassemia allele in the Indian population is IVS-I-5 (G C) (15,16).

Independent reports on the disease's prevalence have been made from a different location with different carrier frequencies in India with different ethnic groups and geographical regions have their own distinctive peculiarities. The frequency and prevalence of the illness in this area have not been well examined in a single depiction. The study outcome on the perspective of beta-thalassemia prevalence in India could change in healthcare policies for building some new approaches to cope with beta-thalassemia-like genetic disorder. So the objective of the study was to depiction the prevalence of thalassemia risk population from pre-published data to determine the heterogeneity and effective proportion.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Guidelines

The pre-published data were gathered from PubMed, Embase and google scholar following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) exclusion and inclusion method with a time frame of 2012 to 2022 and excluding cross-sectional and observational studies.

2.2 Selection of Studies and Data Extraction

Data were extracted with a key word, "the prevalence of beta-thalassemia carrier, India." Based on derived 72 Embase and 49 PubMed studies, 45 studies followed all the inclusion criteria. A final comma-separated valued (CSV) table (Supplementary table S1) was prepared, including the first author's name, publication year, sample size, and prevalence of beta-thalassemia and location of screening camp. Three subdivisions of studies are depicted: institutional studies, local random studies, and hospital-based studies.

2.3. Statistical analysis.

The fixed and random effects models were derived with a confidence interval of 95% (95% CI). The study was conducted using "tidyverse," "meta," "metaphor," "metaprop" and "metaviz" packages of The Comprehensive R Archive Network, version 4.02 and jamovi 2.3.2.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Study Characteristics.

Forty-five studies were included in the meta-analysis which were published over the course of 10 years. For subgroup analysis 16 were carried out in different educational institutions, eight were carried out in different medical facilities and 21 studies were conducted in different localities through-out India. The results are provided in table Supplementary table S1.

3.2. Meta-Analysis Outcomes

A mixed-effects model was used in the meta-analysis to show an $I^2 > 99.99\%$ and p-value. The forest plot shows that the prevalence rate of the disease in this meta-analysis was 0.4238. $I^2 = 99.99\%$; Table 1 and Table 2 show the p-value.

2.3. Statistical analysis.

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Table 1-Mixed-Effects Model (k = 45)

	Estimate	se	Z	p	CI Lower Bound	CI Upper Bound
Intercept	0.1898	0.0288	6.599	<.001	0.1334	0.2462
Moderator	-0.0561	0.0418	-1.3442	0.179	-0.1380	0.0257

Note. Tau² Estimator: Restricted Maximum-Likelihood

Table 2-Heterogeneity Statistics

Tau	Tau ²	I ²	H ²	R ²	df	Q	p
0.1777	0.0316 (SE= 0.0069)	99.99%	14578.6851	0.59%	44.0000	88716.5872	<.001

Figure. 1: Forest plot with events rate and subgroup based on study location

3.3 Publication Bias

Fail-safe N Calculation was used with the Rosenthal Approach to estimate the publication bias and funnel plot. The shape of the funnel plot (Figure. 2) revealed obvious evidence of significance. The value for Fail-safe N was 2072159.0000 and $p < 0.001$ with Plot asymmetry of 4.5972, which is also significant $p < 0.001$ (Table 3).

Table 3-Publication Bias Assessment

Fail-Safe N Analysis (File Drawer Analysis)	
<i>Fail-safe N</i>	<i>p</i>
2072159.0000	<0.001
Note. Fail-safe N Calculation Using the Rosenthal Approach	
Regression Test for Funnel Plot Asymmetry	
<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>
4.5972	<0.001
Rank Correlation Test for Funnel Plot Asymmetry	
<i>Kendall's Tau</i>	<i>p</i>
-0.1143	0.269

Figure. 2: Funnel plot with standard error with logit event rate

4. DISCUSSION

The prevalence of beta-thalassemia was estimated for each study, with the number of reported cases as a proportion. A subsequent subgroup analysis was performed based on each location. The overall prevalence rate of beta-thalassemia occurrence in this meta-analysis was 0.4238 (95% CI = 0.1334–0.2462; $I^2 = 99.99\%$; $p < 0.001$). The shape of the funnel plot (Figure 2) revealed obvious evidence of asymmetry. The value for Fail-safe N was 2072159.0000 and $p < 0.001$.

There isn't enough data on how people respond to know they have a genetic susceptibility to illnesses. Evidence suggests that a characteristic is inherited from parents to children, which may result in negative effects. This study will elucidate the pockets of high prevalence zone in India. The asymmetry in the subgroup study shows the neediness of more cosmopolitan screening drive.

Mandatory Premarital Screening and Genetic Counseling Programs (PMSGC), a successful model for several Middle Eastern nations, are needed and government engagement, since social beliefs and discomfort also affect this situation. Genetic counseling is provided to at-risk couples to make sure they are aware of the reproductive risks and options. Prenatal diagnosis (PND) and therapeutic abortion, where permitted, are two methods used by PMSGC programs to reduce the number of births to individuals with beta-thalassemia (65). National career registration, PND programs, and genetic counseling are important adaptations that successful nations have put in place. In India, the registration procedures are scattered and unmonitored and need for a registration program and follow-up to combat the disease.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The beta-thalassemia lead to serious health and financial burden. Efforts need to demonstrate the scenario of prevalence to develop awareness-raising and screening initiatives. Present study will be very relevant to reveal the burden of beta thalassemia in India.

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Table S1: Depiction of studies with proportion and location of study.

author	year	authoryear	cases	total	study	studyarea
Colah	2010	Colah 2010	287	10647	1	institution
Colah	2010	Colah R 2010	280	8004	1	institution
Sachdev	2010	Sachdev 2010	327	2600	3	local
Roa	2010	Roa 2010	257	800	2	hospital
Patel	2012	Patel 2012	6198	317539	3	local
Patel	2012	Patel 2012	1446	32857	1	institution
Dolai	2012	Dolai 2012	3675	35413	1	institution
Jain	2012	Jain 2012	1121	3823	1	institution
Patal	2012	Patal 2012	26964	317539	3	local
Shrivastav	2013	Shrivastav 2013	1615	7261	1	institution
Madan	2013	Madan 2013	449	11090	1	institution
Mohanty	2013	Mohanty 2013	1578	56780	3	local
Das	2013	Das 2013	255	1498	3	local
Kulkarni	2013	Kulkarni 2013	18	210	2	hospital
Philip	2013	Philip J,2013	688	4335	2	hospital
Chaudhury	2013	Chaudhury 2013	3627	14145	2	hospital
Mandal	2014	Mandal 2014	5867	50487	3	local
Pant	2014	Pant 2014	290	4800	3	local
Baruah	2014	Baruah 2014	5320	9000	3	local
Mondal	2014	Mondal 2014	10313	79897	2	hospital
Mondal	2014	Mondal 2014	10313	90210	2	hospital
Goswami	2014	Goswami 2014	889	1872	3	local
Choudhuri	2014	Choudhuri 2014	2193	20883	3	local
Choudhuri	2014	Choudhuri 2014	5867	50487	3	local
Mohanty	2015	Mohanty 2015	1828	15200	3	local
Bhalodia	2015	Bhalodia 2015	43	500	1	institution
Mukhopadhyay	2015	Mukhopadhyay 2015	1509	10407	1	institution
Alam	2015	Alam 2015	208	313	1	institution
Mendiratta	2015	Mendiratta 2015	79	1000	2	hospital
Naskar	2015	Naskar 2015	664	5156	3	local
Chatterjee	2015	Chatterjee 2015	2115	18166	3	local

Mondal	2016	Mondal 2016	14532	119336	3	local
Chakrabarti	2016	Chakrabarti 2016	286	3500	2	hospital
Bhattacharyya	2016	Bhattacharyya 2016	2769	21137	3	local
Warghade	2018	Warghade 2018	12099	65779	3	local
Mishra	2018	Mishra 2018	237	435	1	institution
Ray	2019	Ray 2019	10745	21371	3	local
Chattopadhyay	2019	Chattopadhyay 2019	134	899	3	local
Sorathiya	2020	Sorathiya 2020	90	1000	3	local
Maji	2020	Maji 2020	35404	287258	1	institution
Singh	2020	Singh 2020	149	510	1	institution
Das	2020	Das 2020	689	1076	1	institution
Sorathiya	2020	Sorathiya 2020	102	1000	3	local
Sahu	2021	Sahu 2021	1380	2332	1	institution
Samanta	2021	Samanta 2021	385	2984	1	institution

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